

So you want to publish academic research

History

The background is quite simple: someone (usually a professional academic) studies their specialist subject area, then writes up what they've found as a manuscript. Assuming other people are interested in the research and want to read it, someone now needs to take responsibility for distributing the manuscript.

In ye olden days, a "journal" would compile manuscripts into printed issues, typeset them in the journal's font and layout, then send them out to universities and individual subscribers by post. The submission process was simple: the researchers sent their paper manuscript to the postal address of the journal, who handled everything else.

To reduce distribution costs and ensure that people wanted to subscribe, journals were selective about which manuscripts got included in their issues. To distribute this filtering work, the journal would send copies of the manuscript by post to several people working in the same area - these "peers" would review the manuscript and send back their recommendation on whether the manuscript should be accepted (perhaps after revision).

All this postal to-and-fro took time, and people were eager to read about the work! So, while all this was going on, the authors would send the same "preprint" manuscript directly to university libraries, and to interested colleagues, so that people could start building upon it and research could progress.

When computers and the internet arrived, distributing manuscripts became much easier. A journal just needed an email address to accept submissions, and the electronic documents could be sent out to peer reviewers with minimal delay. There was no need to compile manuscripts into issues, as they could be published online via the web as soon as they were accepted.

Reading and understanding the work still took time, though, especially in mathematically-intense areas like astrophysics, so authors continued sending preprints directly to colleagues by email (the plain-text TeX format was ideal for this; it could be compiled to Postscript for printing by the recipient).

[Mailing lists started up](#), as key people became distribution hubs for preprints in their specialist areas. Subscribers would be a step ahead of everyone else, as they'd get to read research first, and the authors wanted to reach a wide audience, so it's easy to see why this was successful!

More mailing lists were started, and some [started to archive the preprint files](#) so that they could be accessed later: first on FTP servers, then - once WorldWideWeb.app appeared - on HTTP servers, with landing pages showing the metadata and ready-to-read PDF files for download.

Aside: self-publishing and self-archiving

Now that we have the WWW, crawlers, harvesters, indexers and search engines, why don't researchers publish their manuscripts themselves on their own web servers? With collaborative editing in Google Docs (and other, more technical, editors like Overleaf), it couldn't be easier to publish research.

One reason is that most manuscripts are created by collaboration rather than a single author, so there isn't always an obvious "owner" of each manuscript to take responsibility for the formatting and hosting.

There's also the reluctance of journal publishers to cede control over gatekeeping and certifying manuscripts, which puts self-published manuscripts in a bit of a gray area.

While university libraries are making sterling efforts at collecting, preserving and making available all the research outputs of their institutions, it's a lot of work for each institution to create and maintain a repository. These are often also crippled by publisher embargoes and are usually not the first place someone would look for new research.

One more reason is that the (La)TeX format itself can be prohibitive to authors in fields that don't require mathematical formulae, and other text-based formats like Markdown still take some learning. Still, there are [attempts](#) to make it easier for authors to publish their own manuscripts on the web as HTML.

Let's build a preprint server

Hosting preprint manuscripts should be simple: provide an email address for receiving submissions, buy a domain name and unlimited hosting from Dreamhost for \$10/month, put the manuscript PDF files in a folder and point the web server at them.

Of course, it's not quite that simple. There are a few other things to consider:

Metadata

At some point, you'll want to generate a paginated index of all the manuscripts. This requires metadata for each article in a machine-readable format.

Sadly, authors are still being asked to enter this information manually into forms, even though the information is already present on the first page of the manuscript.

A decent preprint server should be able to generate metadata from the manuscript PDF.

Needed: a service that reliably extracts title, authors, affiliations and abstract from the first page of any manuscript PDF.

[Google Scholar does this](#) (proprietary), [science.ai does this](#) (proprietary?), [Mendeley and ResearchGate do this](#) using GROBID (open source) with their own enhancements (proprietary), [CiteSeerX does this](#) (open source), [CERMINE does this](#).

Database?

This metadata needs to live somewhere: it could be stored in a file (JSON, YAML) alongside each PDF, or it could be stored in a database.

Once the metadata is stored, a script can run to generate HTML index pages - and a landing page for each manuscript!

Needed: a service that stores project metadata and files.

[Firebase](#) provides a hosted database and file storage.

Preprint servers are being built on [the OSF platform](#).

Needed: a service that generates HTML pages from a collection of metadata.

[Jekyll](#) does this, and is used in [GitHub Pages](#).

Firebase provides JSON, which can be used to render HTML client-side.

Versioning

Each manuscript needs an overarching "project", to contain different versions of the manuscript as it gets updated. Once the author creates that project, they can upload and submit their manuscript file(s). This "project" could be a folder in a filesystem, or an entry in a database table/collection.

For the sake of permanence, it should be possible to create stable, versioned "releases".

For examples of release versioning see [git tags](#), [GitHub "releases"](#), [semver](#) and [npm](#).

Conversion

If conversion between different formats is a requirement, the author should be able to upload their files in their preferred input format (LaTeX, a Word or OpenOffice document, Markdown, HTML; possibly with separate figure image files), and the system should be able to convert it to the preferred output formats (PDF, HTML).

Needed: a service for conversion of input files to PDF (and, ideally, HTML).

[Pandoc](#) does this, as do several online services.

[rtf2latex2e](#) is good at conversion from RTF to LaTeX.

Alternatively, do everything (input and output) as PDF, and only convert to other formats when *really* needed.

Needed: a service that does close-to-lossless conversion from PDF to HTML.

Acrobat's conversion from PDF to HTML is good; uses [Solid Framework](#).

[pdf2htmlEX](#) and [PDF.js](#) are alternatives.

Alternatively, forget about PDFs: author and publish everything with HTML and JavaScript!

Data?

There may be supplemental files (or just data files) accompanying the manuscript. There are places that these could be hosted separately (figshare, Zenodo, Dryad), or they may be hosted alongside the manuscript. Ideally, the data is all in a separate citable, version-controlled repository, archived for posterity.

Needed: acceptance for publishing data as a separate entity and citing it in several manuscripts.

Permanence

Each project must have a permanent unique identifier (which can be a URL, or a DOI), as should each version of the manuscript.

Needed: a service that archives projects, wherever they're published - each version of a manuscript, with associated metadata and files.

Coming soon: [ASAPbio](#)

Related: [UK Web Archive](#)

Needed: a standard for publishing a list of all published items, latest updated first.

OAI-PMH exists, but needs to be replaced with something better.

A CSV file listing "updated" (id or timestamp/datetime) and "url" for each item is sufficient.

Needed: metadata for each item, in the HTML page as either HTML5 microdata, RDFa or embedded JSON-LD.

<https://schema.org/ScholarlyArticle>

<http://ns.science.ai/>

Metrics and the ecosystem

Authors, funders and readers like to see metrics (views/downloads, likes, mentions, citations), even if they're only rough numbers.

Most of these can be provided by third-parties (e.g. Altmetric, ImpactStory), who are able to normalise all the URLs and unique identifier(s) for each project/version.

Needed: a service that collects and normalises web traffic logs for academic reporting, filtering out crawlers and other gaming.

Needed: a service that provides aggregated metrics for all versions of a project, wherever they're hosted.

[Crossref is about to start linking preprint DOIs to final article DOIs.](#)

Discussion of the manuscript can happen in many places, including formal citations, and can be aggregated as long as each mention has an identifier (URL) for the thing being mentioned.

Needed: a service that aggregates all mentions of a work.

eLife and bioRxiv use Disqus for commenting.

Hypothes.is and Genius provide annotation overlays for any HTML page or PDF file.

Annotations can be aggregated by grouping URLs for each document.

Wikipedia provides an interface for retrieving pages that link to a domain or URL.

Altmetric aggregates news, blogs, social media and some other sources of mentions.

Credit

To ensure that authors get credit for their work, there should be a unique identifier for each contributor.

Needed: a service that converts authors + affiliations to ORCID identifiers.

Identifiers for institutions and funders are also useful

[GRID](#) has identifiers for institutions

[Open Funder Registry](#) has identifiers for funders

Licensing

Either guide authors through a choice of license, or impose a single license (usually CC BY) on all works.

Needed: a service that helps authors choose appropriate license(s) for their manuscripts and data.

e.g. <http://choosealicense.com/>

Filtering

There's some level of filtering (some automated, some manual) even before "peer review", depending on the field. The line between "acceptable" and "unacceptable" is problematic and expensive to maintain.

Needed: a service that provides semi-automated spam filtering.

[arXiv does this](#), using an automated system to provide a first-pass screen of submissions.

Needed: many services (human or machine) that create their own, public filters

[Overlay journals](#)

[Discrete Analysis](#) (via [Scholastica](#))

[The Open Journal](#)

Needed: services that perform post-publication peer review

[Publons](#)

[PubPeer](#)

[ShortScience.org](#)

Needed: a service that aggregates post-publication peer reviews

[Altmetric?](#)